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Design of a Hydraulic Turbine Based in a Pressure Swirl Chamber using Ansys CFD

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Abstract. This study presents the simulation of internal flow of a hydraulic turbine using CFD based on pressure-swirl atomizer technology, typically used in combustion chambers of rocket engines. The proposed model is equipped with a swirl chamber with stabilizer included, dual manifold system and a rotor, each of these elements will be simulated to validate its functionality, prior to implementation and subsequent experimental testing. The results show that it is possible to produce the spray output jet even if there are interferences within the swirl chamber such as the rotor itself and the stabilizer. In addition, due to the tangential speeds produced within the atomizer may be viable to place a rotor to produce mechanical power. This study serves as a starting point to carry out future experimental tests to validate the generated power and efficiency of the proposed system. The results presented in the document were validated using mathematical equations and numerical simulations using the Ansys Fluent software.

1. Introduction

Effective control of fluid distribution in atomization systems is essential for improving industrial efficiency in various areas such as aeronautics and combustion [1],[2]. This paper proposes replacing traditional jet atomizers with pressure-swirl atomizers that use a dual-level manifold system to generate a controlled vortex in a cylindrical chamber. The manifold proposed, with eight strategically positioned inlet channels, ensures uniform fluid flow and stability.

There are lots of mathematical models that predicts small-scale atomizer performance, enabling design refinement for specific environments. However, there are no mathematical models or studies based on large-scale atomizers, which is why the use of CFD tools such as Ansys Fluent is essential. Previous studies show that numerical simulations improve control over fluid behavior, achieving a consistent spray cone angle of 36° to 140° [3] and expanding coverage allows fewer atomizers to achieve better fluid distribution than conventional designs, reducing liquid consumption and operational complexity.

The design proposed follows the theoretical framework based on the fundamental theory developed by Abramovich [4], focusing on mass and momentum conservation of an inviscid liquid inside a cylindrical chamber, this was taken as a starting point to get the general dimensions of the atomizer. Also, this paper was complemented with new theoretical approaches as demonstrated by Ronceros [5-7] including a new important correction parameter which is related to the swirl angle “ β ” and helix angle “ ψ ” and its influence on the control of direction and tangential speed of the fluid in a conical injector. In addition, it was considered [8] the study of pressure swirl atomizers varying geometrical parameters like the number of inlet channels “ n ” and the opening parameter “ C ”, where it was proven that to improve the uniformity of the liquid film thickness is necessary to increase the number of

inlets. Related to this aspect, [9] carried out a study increasing the entry pressure to the inlet channels and its close relationship with a reduction in fluid film thickness. Finally, [10],[11] delimited their study based on the effect of viscosity of the fluid and its relationship with flow rate, analysing the behaviour of liquids with high viscosity when tested in hydraulic atomizers.

Fig. 1: Plan view of swirl chamber with 8 channels

Fig. 2: 3D design of the proposed mechanism for future experimental validation

2. Description of the proposed method

As was mentioned, the principle governing an atomizer is delimited by the swirl motion within a chamber which is intrinsically related to spray quality [12]. In that sense, the key element such as vortex formation, fluid velocity (v), pressure differential (ΔP), and the thickness of the water particle during atomization are integrated into the analysis of the pressure-swirl atomizer [5]. Based on these values, the main dimensions of the atomizer are defined: the swirl chamber radius "Rs" and the outlet nozzle radius "ro"(Fig. 1).

It is necessary to consider, based on this theory, the theoretical design of a hydraulic turbine is proposed (Fig. 2), considering smoother materials to mitigate its effect on velocity distribution and friction losses [13]. The system consists of a pair of flanged supply manifolds for each level, to adequately distribute the flow in each inlet channel. Also, is shown a swirl chamber with a stabilizer included in the base, a rotor, and a shaft. The objective is to describe the internal flow by dividing the analysis of the prototype's internal flow into 3 cases: chamber with stabilizer, feeding manifold and swirl chamber with stabilizer and rotor included (estimating generated power), in order to have a starting point prior to carrying out future experimental tests.

Finally, the figure 3 shows the design process, starting with parameters obtained through a mathematical model that considers the dynamic fluid losses within the multi-level inlet configuration of the pressure-swirl atomizer, considering an appropriate chamber height to reduce the effects of length in the liquid thickness film [14]. The internal flow behavior is accurately simulated using Ansys Fluent, providing a detailed analysis of the fluid movement through the channels.

Fig. 3: Block diagram of the process

2.1. Parameters of design for pressure-swirl atomizer with dual-level inlet

The operating parameters of the pressure-swirl atomizer, which has 8 inlet channels ($n=8$) distributed across two levels, and a spray angle cone of $2\alpha=120^\circ$ (Table 1). The differential pressure is $\Delta P = 350$ kPa. These parameters are critical for ensuring uniform fluid distribution and efficient atomization within the dual-level configuration.

Table 1. Operation parameters of Pressure-Swirl

ΔP (kPa)	m (kg/s)	n	2α ($^\circ$)	C
350	3.5	8	120	2

2.2. Dimensions of atomizer

The spray angle (2α) serves as the initial parameter in determining the atomizer's filling coefficient (φ), which quantifies the volume of liquid in the swirl chamber relative to the air core formed within it. This filling coefficient (φ) is a key design factor in dual-level pressure-swirl atomizers, as it defines the relationship between the annular section of the liquid film $\pi(ro^2 - ra^2)$ and the atomizer's exit area πro^2 (Fig. 2) [6]. Equation (1) expresses this coefficient, which can be calculated using the known spray angle (2α) [15]. With this data, the discharge coefficient "Cd" (Equation 2) and the geometrical parameter "A" (Equation 3) for the pressure-swirl atomizer can be determined [6], which represents the relationship between angular and axial momentum, this parameter is closely related to the main dimensions of the atomizer. These calculations are essential for deriving the atomizer's main dimensions under ideal flow conditions, ensuring optimal performance (Table 1).

$$\varphi = 1 - \left(\frac{ra}{ro}\right)^2 \tag{1}$$

$$Cd = \sqrt{\frac{\varphi^3}{2-\varphi}} \tag{2}$$

$$A = \frac{\sqrt{2}(1-\varphi)}{\varphi\sqrt{\varphi}} \tag{3}$$

Fig.4: Aerodynamic Dragon the Spray of Dual Level Pressure-Swirl

2.3. Available hydraulic power and efficiency

According to the design theory of hydraulic turbines, it is possible to calculate the available hydraulic power of any hydraulic resource if the flow and hydraulic head data are known. However, this formula can be simplified, in terms of flow rate and pressure (Equation 4), which is beneficial due to the research focus.

$$P_H = P \cdot Q \tag{4}$$

2.4. Mesh conditions

Table 2. Mesh configuration for each analysis case

Mesh	Number of elements	Type
Chamber swirl without rotor	1,446,057	Poly-Hex core (Fluent meshing)
Manifolds	2,592,618	Tetrahedral (Workbench meshing)
Chamber swirl with rotor	3,895,549	Tetrahedral (Workbench meshing)

3. Simulation Results

The numerical simulation in Fluent for the first and third cases was configured based on the homogeneous multiphase model: Volume of Fluid and a standard k-epsilon viscous model. This setup aimed to effectively observe the formation of the air core and the spray angle of the outlet jet. Additionally, the surface tension coefficient was set as constant, with a value of 0.073 N/m, and the properties of both fluids (water and air) were considered at room temperature. The turbulence intensity at the inlets was left at the default value of 5%, and the hydraulic diameter matched the diameter of the atomizer's inlet channels: 7 mm.

3.1. Internal flow of the dual-level pressure swirl atomizer without rotor

The validation process was carried out considering design inlet pressure of 350kpa. It is observed that the maximum tangential velocities of 17.7 m/s near the walls of the swirl chamber (Fig. 5). In contrast, the minimum velocity magnitudes of the particles in the outlet jet are 11.8 m/s. Figure 6 illustrates the formation of the air core and the spray angle. As expected, a small portion of the outgoing fluid tends to adhere to the walls of the stabilizer and produces velocity negative values (due to the air core), resulting in only slight alterations to the liquid's shape before exiting as a spray.

Fig.5: Internal flow within the swirl chamber with stabilizer at the outlet

Fig.6: Atomizer volume fraction with VOF, with stabilizer at the outlet

3.2. Mass flow rate

The figure 7 indicate that the mass flow rate at the outlet is not significantly altered compared to the mathematical model with a free outlet structure, showing only a difference of 0.45 kg/s. Similarly, the figure 8 confirms the continuity principle by yielding a negligible value in the net results.

Fig.7: Mass flow rate at each inlet of the atomizer with stabilizer

Fig.8: Mass flow rate at each inlet and outlet of the atomizer with stabilizer

3.3. Internal flow of a manifold in a dual-level pressure swirl atomizer

The dynamics of the internal flow within the manifolds of a dual-level pressure swirl atomizer are crucial for ensuring efficient fluid distribution before it enters the swirl chamber. The design of the manifolds directly influences the distribution of tangential velocity and pressure gradients throughout the system. As shown in Figure 9, the static pressure necessary to adequately feed the atomizer with a flow of 3.9l/s (validated in the previous section) is 416 kPa. Also, it is also shown that the pressure in the 8 outlet injectors is around 341kpa, which is consistent with the design pressure previously considered. Also, it is observed that the distribution of velocities at the manifold outlet take values close to 17.4m/s in Figure 10. A small area at the top of the second injector shows that the velocity near the wall is zero, because the curvature of the injector is slightly further apart (compared to the other 3) from the principal distributor. However, this phenomenon does not seem to greatly affect the speed distribution of the 2 final injectors.

Fig.9: Static pressure within the feed manifolds

Fig.10: Velocity magnitude within the feed manifold

3.4. Mass flow rate

The simulated inlet flow data of the 3.9l/s channels developed in section 3.1 was taken to evaluate manifold performance. The figure 11 indicate that the mass flow rate at the manifold's inlet and outlet in each admission channel. The flow results in each injector show acceptable results, because each channel is fed with approximately 0.5l/s.

Fig.11: Mass flow rate at each inlet and outlet of the manifold

3.5. Internal flow of the dual-level pressure swirl atomizer with rotor

A rotor was implemented in the atomizer to harness the vortex motion of water, occupying nearly the entire diameter of the swirl chamber, as simulations show maximum tangential velocities near the walls. For simulating the internal flow and mechanical power generated by the rotor, the mesh adjustment methods (including smoothing, layering, and remeshing) were activated to accommodate the turbine's movement. To enable rotation, six degrees of freedom (six DOF) for rigid bodies were activated, allowing rotation around the Z-axis. The rotor's mass and moment of inertia (Izz) were calculated using SolidWorks with ABS material. Reports on moment, angular velocity and power were generated, which they going to be used in the next subsection.

The internal flow of the atomizer, which incorporates an internal rotor, shows maximum velocities with orange color inside the chamber of 19.67 m/s in the entry channels (Fig. 12). The rotor, due to its curvature, significantly supports the swirling motion, contributing to taking advantage the moderate velocities observed near the chamber walls from 9.17 m/s to 5.24 m/s. The multiphase behavior between water and air at the outlet of the swirl chamber remains as expected, since the formation of a stable spray angle is observed, which contributes to a more uniform and well-defined spray pattern (Fig. 13). However, Although the atomization effect at the chamber outlet is totally visible, the addition of the rotor greatly affected the formation of the air core, making it practically nonexistent.

Fig. 12: Internal flow within the swirl chamber with rotor included and stabilizer at the outlet

Fig. 13: Atomizer volume fraction with VOF, with rotor included and stabilizer at the outlet

3.6. Power simulation

The maximum angular velocity obtained was 120 rad/s, after a few milliseconds it decayed and stabilized at 100 rad/s (Figure 14).

Fig. 14: Rotor's resulting angular velocity.

Because the torque suffers from small oscillations, it was decided to maintain the simulation for a few additional seconds, in order to stabilize its behavior. It is observed that the maximum peak moment is approximately 10Nm obtained in the first 0.5 seconds of simulation, the torque decreases until it stabilizes at 8.5Nm, having small oscillations (Figure 15). The same behavior is obtained in the Figure 16 where the power suffers a shock in the first moments and stabilizes at 855W.

Fig. 15: Resulting moment using dynamic mesh

Fig. 16: Proposed system power generated

3.7. Mechanical efficiency calculation

To calculate the efficiency of the system, equation 4 is used, the inlet pressure to which the atomizer was subjected (350kPa) is considered, and the total intake flow (3.9l/s) through all channels, to obtain the available hydraulic power of the fluid.

$$P_H = 350000 \cdot 0.0039 = 1365W$$

$$n = \frac{855}{1365} = 0.626$$

4. Conclusion

The computational analysis shown for the first case shows consistent results with the design of the swirl chamber using mathematical models, demonstrating that the addition of a stabilizer at the outlet of the atomizer does not greatly impact fluid consumption, specifically showing a difference in the mass flow of 0.45kg/s compared to the conventional mathematical model. Also, regarding the second case that consists of a feeding manifold, it is necessary to highlight that the proposed model meets the objective of equitably distributing the water to the inlet channels of the atomizer around 0.5kg/s per each one. Finally, the third case, about the swirl chamber with stabilizer and rotor included, shows that it is possible to produce an atomization effect at the output of the system, even if there are obstacles inside the chamber, and due to tangential velocities (around 9.1m/s) it is possible to take advantage of it using a rotor, which can take advantage of 62.6% of available energy, according to simulations. All the above is taken as a starting point to carry out the validation of future experimental tests, where an exhaustive energy generation analysis of the proposed system may be possible.

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